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Partnership: An Essential Ingredient in an Adviser's Work

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Having a strong foundation in partnership can significantly impact the lives of our learners. The emergence of pedagogical concepts of partnership as a source of trust in fostering closer relationships during counseling has sealed the way for various methods in counseling programs.

Trusting relationships with clients lead to more accurate and comprehensive counseling based on genuine information shared by them. Cheung (2019) described community engagement through 'deliberative democracy' as a crucial tool in building trust. For instance, a couple seeking advice regarding their rebellious adolescent son can receive a more effective resolution if both parents actively collaborate with the school adviser. This collaboration involves sharing problems encountered during the child's earlier years, leading up to his current state of being difficult and disoriented. Issues that are both mental and experiential should be disclosed to apply appropriate methods tailored to the young man's developmental stage. Thus, deliberative democracy refers to the proactive involvement of concerned individuals or immediate family members who seek recommendations or solutions to life challenges.

How do we create partnerships with the parents of our learners? For me, partnership involves key factors such as trust, confidence, and empathy. Trust builds confidence, which can be gained through constant dialogue and communication. Empathy should be demonstrated by listening, consistent probing, and showing approval. It is essential to spend sufficient time with parents and learners to truly understand their situations and put oneself in their shoes. When parents trust the classroom advisor, openness will come more easily, and confidentiality will be established.

Furthermore, three key guiding principles can be derived from partnership: respect, reciprocity, and shared responsibility (Cook-Sather and Felten, 181). Reciprocity is a balanced give-and-take relationship, demonstrated through the sharing of experiences and insights. Healey et al. (2014, pp. 14-15) expanded on the values that foster partnership, which include trust, courage, plurality, responsibility, authenticity, honesty, inclusivity, reciprocity, and empowerment.

The Students as Partners (SaP) model can be highly beneficial in the field of counseling. This philosophy combines various practices and possibilities, offering clients or parents unique opportunities to propose their own solutions to challenges related to their family or studies. It functions as a collaborative approach that simplifies decision-making.

Conclusion

It is a relevant aspect of a life educator's work to practice eclectic pedagogical concepts of partnership as a source of trust in fostering closer relationships during counseling. This approach has paved the way for developing various methods in counseling programs.

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